

The Influence of Service Quality and Promotion on Consumers' Repurchase Decision with Shopping Life Style as a Variable Moderating at Franchise Minimarket in Medan

Conny Ivana Sianturi¹, Dr. Endang S. Rini¹, Dr. Beby K. Fawzee Sembiring¹,
Juhar Monang S. Tambun²

¹Faculty of Economy & Business, Department of Management Science, USU,

²Department of Economy Statistic, Politeknik Statistika STIS

Corresponding Author: Conny Ivana Sianturi

ABSTRACT

The level of sale in franchise minimarkets in Medan City is low comparing with increase in its quantity. It indicates that the quantity does not guarantee the increase in sale. Therefore, attention should be paid to its quality rather than its quantity in Medan. As time and technology developed, its management should pay full attention to people's shopping lifestyle in Medan. The objective of the research was to find out and to analyze the influence of service quality and promotion on consumers' repurchase decision with shopping life style moderating variable. The population was 325 franchise mini markets, Indomaret and Alfamart, in 21 sub-districts in Medan. The researcher used two stage cluster random sampling technique so that there were 6 sub-districts and 12 mini markets. The samples were 110 respondents, taken by using accidental sampling technique. The data were analyzed by using moderate regression analysis (MRA). The result of the analysis showed that partially, service quality and promotion had positive and significant influence on consumers' repurchase decision. Shopping lifestyle could moderate the positive and insignificant influence of service quality on consumers' repurchase decision and it could moderate negative and insignificant influence of service quality on consumers' repurchase decision.

Keywords: *Service Quality, Promotion, Shopping Life Style, Consumer's Repurchase Decision*

INTRODUCTION

Business development in the era of globalization is inseparable from increasingly fierce competition in marketing goods and services. Therefore every company is required to always strive to display maximum results so that the goods and services are able to be accepted by the community and survive in the face of similar business competition. Retail is a way

of marketing products that covers all the activities of selling goods directly to end consumers, so that retail is the last link in a distribution process. One form of retail business selling product items is a franchise business. This business is rapidly developing and can be accepted in the community as a means of marketing goods and services. According to data from the International Franchise Association, in 2015

there were around 780 thousand franchises in the world which impacted the opening of 8.9 million jobs in Indonesia. The franchise business is noted to make a positive contribution to the national economy and keep the economy spinning amid the economic downturn. There were 698 franchises in Indonesia with 24,400 outlets consisting of 63% local franchises and 37% overseas with turnover reaching Rp. 172 trillion. In 2017 there were 452 minimarkets in Medan and more than 94 percent were franchised minimarkets, which amounted to 424 minimarkets, such as: Indomaret, Alfamart, Alfamidi, and Giant in Medan, while non-franchise minimarkets only had 28. Following data franchise minimarket spread in 21 sub-districts of Medan. It can be seen in Table 1.1 below.

Table 1.1 Number of Minimarket Franchises in Medan City

No	Name of the Minimarket Franchise	Number of Minimarkets
1	Alfamart	157
2	Alfa Midi	98
3	Giant	1
4	Indomaret	168
Total		424

Source: researcher observations in the field (2017)

Based on the highest number of minimarkets, researchers limit research, which are two tightly competing franchise minimarkets, Indomaret and Alfamart. Some previous studies examined differences in service quality between these two franchise minimarkets. Walangitan (2017) found that in business competition, the positions of Indomaret and Alfamart were always close together. However, these problems are not an obstacle for both. This is because they are in the same market share, sell uniform products and are in a crowd center. The dominant number of Indomaret and Alfamart minimarkets above is assumed to represent the general description in Medan City. Following is the percentage of outlet growth and sales growth of Indomaret and Alfamart franchise minimarkets nationally and locally in Medan City. Can be seen in the following Tables 1.2 and 1.3.

Table 1.2 Percentage of growth of Indomaret and Alfamart franchise outlets nationally and locally in Medan Cit

Retail Name	National percentage		Percentage of Medan City	
	2015-2016	2016-2017	2015-2016	2016-2017
Indomaret	14%	14%	23%	22%
Alfamart	16%	7.7%	12%	85%

Source: Annual report PT. Sumber Alfaria Trijaya Tbk. & PT. Indoritel Makmur International. Tbk, Databoks, Katadata Indonesia

Table 1.3 Percentage of sales growth of Indomaret and Alfamart franchise minimarket nationally and locally in Medan City

Retail Name	National percentage		Percentage of Medan City	
	2015-2016	2016-2017	2014-2015	2015-2016
Indomaret	20%	8.8%	42%	29%
Alfamart	16%	9.4%	6%	46%

Source: Annual report PT. Sumber Alfaria Trijaya Tbk. & PT. Indoritel Makmur International. Tbk, Databoks, Katadata Indonesia

This shows that for now the addition of outlets has not been the right solution to increase sales. Many things must be anticipated to keep up with competition. The thing to be achieved from the business development of franchise minimarkets in Medan is to make a profit. The thing that can be done by the company to get a profit is by increasing sales volume, increasing sales volume does not come by itself, for that companies need to find ways to attract consumers to repurchase. Schiffman and Kanuk (2007: 485), define a purchasing decision "as the selection of an action from two or more alternative choices. A consumer who wants to make a choice then he must have alternative choices. "The consumer decision-making process is an important thing for consumers to buy a product. For consumers, the decision-making process is an important activity because in the process it contains various steps that occur sequentially before the consumer makes a purchase decision.

One retail mix that can influence consumer purchasing decisions according to Utami (2012: 86) is service. Based on the pre survey data above, the service level is still not optimal. Services at Indomaret are felt to be good at 67%, and service at Alfamart is 55%, this figure is good, but not yet maximal, it still has to be improved.

In addition to service quality, promotion is also one of the retail mix mixes that is an important factor in making

consumer purchasing decisions. According to Stanton in Sunyonto (2015: 157) promotion is an element in the company's marketing mix that is utilized to notify, persuade, and remind about the company's products. The intensity of promotion for Indomaret is 61%, and Alfamart is 67%. This figure shows that the buyer still does not know the exact intensity of the promotion carried out by Indomaret and Alfamart, and what promotions are offered by the two minimarkets names. In the current era of modernization, minimarket franchise businesses need to pay attention to the shopping life style of potential customers. Lifestyle is the pattern of one's life in the world revealed in the activities, interests and opinions of Kotler and Keller (2009: 224). Shopping life style can play a role as a factor that can strengthen or weaken the process of consumer purchasing decisions that are presented in the franchise minimarket. An increasingly modern lifestyle greatly influences consumer shopping choices.

This research is based on the results of previous research conducted by Karwur (2016) conducted a study entitled the influence of retail marketing mix on purchasing decisions at Indomaret Paniki, the results of the analysis showed that the retail marketing mix consisted of products, prices, promotions, services, store design, shop location, and store atmosphere simultaneously have a significant effect on consumer purchasing decisions. Afriyani (2017) found products, prices, promotions, significantly affected the decision to repurchase Kalimilk milk products in Yogyakarta. Hasnah (2016) found that lifestyle towards purchasing decisions of hijab at Elzatta Madiun Gallery resulted in negative moderation due to the moderation of these variables did not strengthen the relationship between variables but would weaken the relationship between variables.

Based on the description above, the researcher is interested in conducting research on the extent of the influence of service quality and promotion on consumer

repurchase decisions with shopping life style as a moderating variable in the Medan City franchise minimarket.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Service quality

According to Tjiptono & Chandra (2011: 164), the concept of quality is considered as a measure of the perfection of a product or service consisting of design quality and conformance quality. According to Tjiptono (2011: 3), "the term service implies everything that certain parties do to other parties". So it can be concluded that service / service is an activity or interaction action between the giver and the recipient of the service / service offered by the giver in an intangible manner so that it cannot be felt physically.

According to Parasuraman, (1998) service quality is defined as how far the difference between reality and buyer expectations for the service they receive / obtain. According to Lewis & Booms in Tjiptono & Chandra (2011: 180), service quality is a measure of how well the level of service provided is able to materialize according to the expectations of buyers.

Promotion

Kotler and Armstrong (2014: 76) define promotion as referring to activities that communicate product excellence and persuade potential customers to buy it. Lupiyoadi (2013: 92) defines promotion as an activity carried out by the company to communicate the benefits of the product and as a tool to influence consumers in the activity of buying or using services according to their needs. According to Stanton quoted by Sunyonto (2015: 157), promotion is an element in the company's marketing mix that is utilized to notify, persuade, and remind about the company's products. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2012: 432), the promotion mix consists of 5 (five) promotional tools, namely: Advertising (advertising), Sales promotion (sales promotion), Personal selling (individual sales), Public relations

(public relations), Direct marketing (direct sales).

Repurchase Decision

Schiffman and Kanuk (2007: 485), defines a purchasing decision as the selection of an action from two or more alternative choices. So that when consumers make a brand purchase for the first time, and buy with a smaller amount than usual. This purchase is usually called trial purchase.

Regarding the reasons for repurchase Blackwell et al (2001) argue that when a repurchase appears it means there are two possibilities, namely: repeated purchases in order to solve problems (repeated problem solving), or because of habits in decision making (habitual decision making). According to Blackwell et al. (2001) the repurchase decision is one of the consumer purchasing decisions which among them are influenced by consumer psychological factors.

Based on the description above, it can be concluded that consumer repurchase decisions are consumer behavior in making purchasing decisions that are the same brand as previous purchases, frequency of buying more often and / or buying with a quantity that tends to be higher.

Hypothesis

1. Service quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer repurchase decisions in the Medan City franchise minimarket
2. Promotion has a positive and significant effect on consumer repurchase decisions in the Medan City franchise minimarket
3. Shopping Life Style positively and significantly moderates the influence of service quality on consumer repurchase decisions in the Medan City franchise minimarket
4. Shopping Life Style positively moderates and significantly influences promotion on consumer repurchase decisions in the Medan City franchise minimarket

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Population and Samples

The populations in this study were all buyers at the Indomaret and Alfamart franchise minimarkets in 21 sub-districts of Medan City with 325 minimarkets.

The sampling method for the location of the cluster franchise minimarket is the sampling technique chosen based on certain areas (Sugiyono, 2013: 83). As a result, 6 selected sub-districts are: Medan Deli, Medan Timur, Medan Perjuangan, Medan Kota, Medan Maimun and Medan Polonia. It is assumed that each sub-district has a franchise minimarket (both Indomaret and Alfamart) with the same standard of service quality and promotion in each sub-district in Medan City. The next stage is the selection of minimarkets and respondents, the researchers used two stage cluster random sampling (two-stage random cluster sampling), each of two minimarkets (Alfamart and Indomaret) for each sub-district. The respondent population is infinite, so the researcher limits the research to variable Y (repeat purchase decision) that is the buyer who has bought more than once at the same minimarket, where the buyer is not only the buyer who has the minimarket member card. The researcher assumes the respondents have the same consumption pattern in terms of the characteristics of respondents based on the dominant age in the field (20-26 years), that is, the millennial generation is a generation born between 1980 and 2000 (Naumovska, 2017). Millennials live in an era of high mobility and all connected to the internet, so that it impacts lifestyle, habits, and personal matters. Provetic's research on 4,670 millennial respondents shows that the majority of respondents make shopping one of their priorities (Citra, 2016). Millennials also have great potential in the consumption industry. According to the Central Bureau of Statistics, 35% of the 254.9 million inhabitants of Indonesia are the millennial generation of productive age. Based on these assumptions, the sampling technique used for respondents is accidental sampling.

The sample size of the researcher used Hair theory (1995) which suggested that the appropriate sample size was between 100 and 200. In this study, the number of questions in the research questionnaire was 22 so the number of samples was 5 times the number of questions or as much as $5 \times 22 = 110$. Then the number of samples used is 110 people.

Data analysis method

This research was conducted to test the hypothesis proposed by using research methods that have been designed in accordance with the variables to be studied so that accurate results are obtained. This type of research is quantitative descriptive. According to Sinulingga (2016) that descriptive quantitative research is a type of research that aims to describe systematically, factually and accurately about the facts and the nature of an object or a particular population.

DISCUSSION

Service Quality has a Positive Significant Effect on Consumer Repurchase Decisions

Based on the research that has been done, from the respondent's answers regarding service quality, the average yield of 3.71 shows that the category agrees. This means that the minimarket franchise in order to increase consumer repurchase decisions has implemented the dimensions of service quality in its operational activities. This research is in line with the research conducted by Utomo and Trisnowati (2017). Other research results are in line with the research conducted by Utama and Ngatno (2015). The results show partially that service quality has a positive effect on repurchase decisions (Studies in Gelael Consumer Mall Ciputra Semarang).

Promotion Has Positive and Significant Effects on Consumer Repurchase Decisions

Based on the results of the study, it was found that promotion had a positive and significant effect on consumer repurchase

decisions in the Medan city franchise minimarket. This is due to the average value of the repeat purchase decision, which is doubtful, which is equal to 3.38, this result is also in line with the average value of the promotion variable, which is 3.34 which shows the results of the overall hesitation. Declining promotions in franchise minimarkets will result in a decrease in buyers' repeat purchase decisions, and that is happening now based on data obtained from the field according to respondents in the Medan City franchise minimarket. The minimarket needs to improve the ad so that it is easily understood by the buyer, conduct promotions through events (certain events), regular discounts, and a bazaar to attract buyers. Thus the consumer repurchase decision will also increase even more often shop at the franchise minimarket.

The results of this study are not in line with the research conducted by Hasanah (2015) that partially promotion through catalogs does not significantly influence purchasing decisions in Indomaret Kota Madiun, but supports the results of other studies conducted by Marendra (2018) namely partial test results indicating that promotion significantly influence keputusasan consumer purchases at minimarkets (Alfamart or Indomaret). The results of the same study were also found by Rismawati (2017) that promotion had an effect on purchasing decisions on Alfamart and Indomaret in Dawe District, Kudus Regency.

Shopping Life Style Positively Moderates Not Significant Effect of Service Quality on Consumer Repurchase Decisions

Service quality has a positive and significant effect on direct repurchase decisions, but when moderated by shopping life style variables the results of shopping life style strengthen the relationship of service quality to repeat purchase decisions, it can be seen from the resulting coefficient value (0.062) but not significantly ($0.494 > 0.05$). Currently the shopping life style of the city of Medan is still underdeveloped so that the quality of services provided has not

been affected by the current trend of development so that it has not been able to significantly increase purchasing decisions. But this shopping life style needs to be considered because in the future the trend of shopping in the city of Medan will definitely grow rapidly and can strengthen the influence of service quality on the increase in consumer repeat purchase decisions in the Medan City franchise minimarkets significantly.

This result is in line with the research conducted by Setiawan (2013) where the activity variable in lifestyle does not have a significant effect on purchasing decisions, but this result is not in line with the research conducted by Hasanah (2016) where lifestyle as a moderating variable has a significant effect on purchasing decisions. These results are not in line with the research conducted by Hasanah (2016) where lifestyle as a moderating variable has a significant effect on purchasing decisions.

Shopping Life Style Negatively Negotiates Significant Effect of Promotion on Consumer Repurchase Decisions

Based on the results of the study, it was found that promotion had a positive and significant effect on consumer repurchase decisions in the Medan city franchise minimarket. This is due to the average value of the repeat purchase decision, which is doubtful, which is equal to 3.38, this result is also in line with the average value of the promotion variable, which is 3.34 which shows the results of the overall hesitation. Shopping life style negatively moderates the insignificant effect of promotion on consumer repurchase decisions can be seen from the coefficient value is negative (-0.075) and $\text{sig.} > 0.05$ ($0.428 > 0.05$). This shows that shopping life style as a moderating variable will weaken the effect of promotion on consumer repurchase decisions, although not significantly. For now, seeing the development of shopping life styles in the city of Medan makes the promotion trend in franchise minimarkets currently declining so that it can reduce consumer repurchase decisions at the

Medan City franchise minimarket even though the effect has not yet been felt at this time. Currently the promotional trend is declining so that it can reduce consumer repurchase decisions, this needs to be watched out by the minimarket in order to take concrete action to improve the promotion and adapt it to the Medan city shopping life style, even though the effect is not significant to the Naum repeat purchase decision, for the future if not repaired it will have a negative impact on the minimarket. The minimarkets need to provide clear and easy-to-understand information, improve promotions through regular events, discounts, and provide a consistent bazaar and socialize it, and most importantly, find the right promotional media in line with developments in the current Medan City shopping life style, such as social media.

This result is in line with the research conducted by Hasanah (2016) where lifestyles as a moderating variable weakens the influence of independent variables on consumer repurchase decisions.

CONCLUSION

1. Service quality has a positive and significant effect on consumer repurchase decisions.
2. Promotion has a positive and significant effect on consumer repurchase decisions.
3. Shopping life style moderates the effects of service quality on consumer repurchase decisions positively but not significantly.
4. Shopping life style moderates the effects of promotions on consumer repurchase decisions negatively but not significantly.
5. Suggestion
6. Minimarket franchise in Medan City needs to do a more creative and varied product arrangement to attract more visitors.
7. This retail business is directly related to the end consumer, it is necessary to maintain good relationships with buyers. The minimarket management needs to

optimize the quality of employees in the midst of the consumer's increasingly instant shopping lifestyle and does not like to wait long by providing them with excellent service training and training in technology (computers and the internet) to maintain quality not just the quantity of franchise minimarkets.

8. The minimarket is connected directly to the end consumer; therefore the minimarket needs to make buyers as their promotional tool by providing the best services, such as giving gifts, vouchers, discounts, etc. Thus consumers will tell and invite others to shop at the franchise minimarket.
9. The minimarket needs to pay attention to the current shopping life style of the city of Medan, because it can strengthen the influence of service quality on consumer repurchase decisions even though currently it is not significant but for the future it will be very useful for minimarkets to increase consumer repurchase decisions, namely by giving on line service and 24 hour service.
10. The minimarket party needs to provide clear advertising information, procure promotions through events, procure discounts on a regular basis, and procure a more consistent bazaar and socialize it to buyers when they will hold the bazaar.
11. The minimarket needs to promote the latest facilities and services they have.
12. The minimarket party needs to pay attention to the current shopping life style of the city of Medan, because it can weaken the effect of promotion on consumer repurchase decisions even though it is currently not significant. Currently the promotional trend is declining so that it can reduce consumer repurchase decisions, this needs to be watched out by the minimarket in order to take concrete action to improve promotion and adapt it to the shopping life style of the community.

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How to cite this article: Sianturi CI, Rini ES, Sembiring BKF et.al. The influence of service quality and promotion on consumers' repurchase decision with shopping life style as a variable moderating at franchise minimarket in Medan. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2019; 6(5):32-39.
